

pH-Sensitive Dendrimerosomes of Hybrid Triazine-Carbosilane Dendritic Amphiphiles-Smart Vehicles for Drug Delivery

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DOX release from dendrimerosomes

Figure S1. Kinetic curves of the fluorescence acquisition in the dialysis buffer upon incubation of free doxorubicin and doxorubicin-loaded dendrimerosomes at different pH. Conditions: see Section 2.9.

Dendron biocompatibility

Figure S2. Cell viability profiles after incubation with amphiphilic dendron for 72 h. WST-1 assay. NT–non-treated cells. Data are presented as Mean \pm S.D. (n = 5).

Drug internalization studies

Figure S3. Representative plots of fluorescence distribution in 1301 cells incubated with PBS (non-treated control), blanc dendrimersomes (DS), doxorubicin (DOX) and doxorubicin-loaded dendrimersomes (DOX@DS). Percentages of cells having fluorescence higher than in control are indicated on graphs.

Figure S4. Fluorescence microscopy images of 1301 cells incubated with blank dendrimersomes (DS), doxorubicin (DOX) and doxorubicin-loaded dendrimersomes (DOX@DS). Scale bar represents 20 μm .

Apoptosis induction studies

Figure S5. Representative FACS plots of 1301 cells incubated with PBS (non-treated control), blank dendrimersomes (DS), doxorubicin (DOX) and doxorubicin-loaded dendrimersomes (DOX@DS) followed by staining with FITC-Annexin V and 7-AAD.

¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃)

MS spectrum of the amphiphilic dendron G2

